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Research Article

**SEROPOSITIVITY OF HBV AND HCV PREVALENCE AMONG
DENTAL PATIENTS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH**¹Sarang Suresh, ²Priya Rani, ³Dr. Haroon Arif¹Dental Surgeon RHC Nasirabad²Dental Surgeon Bibi Aseefa Dental College Hospital Larkana³Punjab Dental Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research was to determine the onset of HBV and HCV among patients seeking dental treatment.

Patients and Methods: This cross-sectional research was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from August 2017 to April 2018 which included 400 patients who approached the hospital. Blood samples were screened for Anti-HCV and HBsAg in hospital laboratory by using ICT method in the supervision of an expert technician. Samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for a period of ten minutes at -20°C . HBV screening based on antibodies detection against the associated virus in sera with the help of enzyme immunoassays. HCV test basis on the antibodies which are viral specific in the samples of serum.

Results: In the course of research 400 patients were examined among which there were 180 females (45%) and 220 males (55%). Mean age was (33.61 ± 15.41) years in the age bracket of 15 years – 60 years. The HCV prevalence was 18% and HBS prevalence was 12% among drivers and lab technicians. The prevalence of HBV was 7% and HCV was 7.75%. HBV and HCV were not statistically significant among females and males.

Conclusion: Higher prevalence of HBV & HCV among dental patients puts extreme responsibility on the shoulders on dental professionals in order to arrest cross-infection among patients. It is important to educate professionals about timely referral for better treatment options.

Keywords: HBV, Hepatitis B Virus, HCV, Hepatitis C Virus, Dental and Hepatocellular Carcinoma.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis causes liver inflammation and swelling as it is an infection. The chronic form of Hepatitis may also lead to cancer or cirrhosis. People normally report restricted or no signs; whereas, it also leads to anorexia, jaundice, diarrhoea and poor appetite. Hepatitis is caused due to agents like poison, alcohol, autoimmunity and drugs; whereas, most of the cases are caused due to viruses. HBV is among major world health issues [1]. HBV transmits through sexual contact, blood and its products. Reports are also available about intrafamilial transmission [2]. Other reasons of HCV transmission include contaminated instruments, contaminated needles, unsafe medical practice, unsafe transfusion of blood, armpit shaving, face shaving, intravenous drug, barbers using unsterilized instruments, ear piercing, nose piercing, unqualified treatment and poor personal hygiene [3, 4]. Most importantly, the main cause of HCV transmission is an improper screening of the blood for onward transfusion [5].

Both HBV & HCV are among major contributors of severe liver disease which include cirrhosis related end-stage liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to WHO estimates the chronic HBV infection is prevalent among 350 million people and chronic HCV infection is reported in 170 million all over the world [6]. A huge amount of deaths is also attributed to HBV and HCV every year [7]. Pakistan is among high-risk groups as 6% – 12% prevalence of HBV and 15% – 25% HCV. Moreover, five percent population carries HCV chronically and three percent HBV chronic carriers [8]. Different countries present different rate of prevalence of HBV and HCV. Different countries produce HBV and HCV burden in the bracket of 5% – 10% [9].

The aim of this research was to determine the onset of HBV and HCV among patients seeking dental treatment.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional research was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from August 2017 to April 2018 which included 400 patients who approached the hospital. Research commenced after institutional ethical approval and consent of the patient. Blood samples were screened for Anti-HCV and HBsAg in hospital laboratory by using ICT method in the supervision of an expert technician. Samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for a period of ten minutes at -20° C. HBV screening based on antibodies detection against the associated virus in sera with the help of enzyme immunoassays. HCV test basis on the antibodies which are viral specific in the samples of serum. The research included every patient who approached for the treatment without any exclusion criteria on the basis of gender and age. Only those patients who were already diagnosed for HBV and HCV were not made a part of this research. We also assured the patients about the confidentiality of their reports. Positive cases were given advice and treatment. They were sent to specialists for proper screening and treatment. Data were analyzed through SPSS.

RESULTS:

In the course of research 400 patients were examined among which there were 180 females (45%) and 220 males (55%). Mean age was (33.61 ± 15.41) years in the age bracket of 15 years – 60 years. The HCV prevalence was 18% and HBS prevalence was 12% among drivers and lab technicians. The prevalence of HBV was 7% and HCV was 7.75%. HBV and HCV were not statistically significant among females and males.

Outcomes are reflected in Table – I (Age Distribution), Table – II (Occupation Wise HBV & HCV Seropositivity), Table – III (Overall HBV & HCV Seropositivity) and Table (Gender Wise HBV & HCV Prevalence).

Table – I: Age Distribution

Age	Number	Percentage
15 – 20 Years	40	10.00
21 – 30 Years	165	41.25
31 – 40 Years	95	23.75
41 – 50 Years	80	20.00
51 – 60 Years	20	5.00
Total	400	100

Table – II: Occupation Wise HBV & HCV Seropositivity

Occupation	Total	HCV Positive		HBS Positive	
		No	%	No	%
House wives	70	5	7.14	3	4.28
Driver	80	8	10	8	10
Teacher	60	2	3	3	5
Student	100	3	3	4	4
Lab. Technician	50	9	18	6	12
Laborer	40	4	10	4	10

Table – III: Overall HBV & HCV Seropositivity

Total		HCV Positive		HBV Positive	
Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
400	100	31	7.75	28	7

Table – IV: Gender Wise HBV & HCV Prevalence

Sero-Positive Patients	Male		Female		X2	P-value
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage		
HCV Positive (31)	18	8.18	13	7.22	1.237	0.539
HBV Positive (28)	17	7.72	11	6.11	1.778	0.655

DISCUSSION:

Studies have discussed HCV antibodies and HB surface antigen (HBsAg). Outcomes differ according

to population and outcomes generalization. Different studies are required as the populations differ in terms of culture and socioeconomic status [6, 8, 10, 11]. The

aim of this research was to determine the onset of HBV and HCV among patients seeking dental treatment.

Ansari-Moghaddam also studied HCVAb and HBsAg and reported risk factors, sex and age. Their reported HBsAg seroprevalence was 2.5% and seroprevalence of HCVAb was 0.5%. HBsAg significantly increases with age; whereas, it is not the same for HCVAb (P-Values < 0.001, 0.67). There was no dominance of males or females in terms of HBsAg or HCVAb prevalence (P-Values =0.15, 0.27). We only targeted the prevalence of HBV and HCV. Higher prevalence was reported in research conducted by Ansari-Moghaddam which reported HBV as 7% and HCV as 7.75% for both genders. Possible reasons for HBV and HCV prevalence includes awareness lack of screening and vaccination.

Another international research presented contrary outcomes about HCVAb as 29.6% and HBsAg as 4.9% [13]. Higher prevalence has also been reported in thalassemic patients specifically for HCVAb and HBsAg with respective proportions of 14.4% and 13.5%. HBsAg prevalence among blood donors, pregnant women and barbers was respectively 16%, 6.5% and 31.4% [14].

Shahid Jamil reported anti HCV antibodies presence by using Immuno-chromatographic approach and he also administered a questionnaire for awareness and knowledge. They reported their outcomes by studying 394 females (61%) and 254 males (39%). An overall HCV prevalence was reported among 67 patients (10.3%) among which 30 were males (11.8%) and 37 were females (9.4%).

Ataei studies drivers and co-drivers and conducted screening of Hbc-Ab, HBs-Ag and HCV-Ab through Elisa method; further confirmation was carried out through RIBA test for positive cases of ELISA method. Risk factors were not different between those individuals who were infected by HCV and HBV. We screened HBV and HCV seropositivity through ICT method.

CONCLUSION:

Higher prevalence of HBV & HCV among dental patients puts extreme responsibility on the shoulders on dental professionals in order to arrest cross-infection among patients. It is important to educate professionals about timely referral for better treatment options.

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